

Data Pitch

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D4.2 Summary of round 1

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1. Executive summary

The overall goal of Data Pitch is to accelerate the European data ecosystem, creating and supporting new businesses by unlocking the commercial potential of high-value datasets in a transnational, cross-sectoral data innovation ecosystem. This document describes the call for the first round accelerator for Data Pitch which will be coordinated and led by WP4. We cover the activities starting with the publication of the call to the invitation of the successful SMEs to the accelerator launch event in London. There are two acceleration phases in Data Pitch. These calls are the main actions contained within the project. Other activities support the acceleration phases and build upon their impact.

A call was put out for SMEs ready to exploit the potential of data not available in the public domain. Applications were to be made via <http://datapitch.eu/apply/> and following the steps described there. The F6S platform for founders and investors was used for the submission mechanism: <https://www.f6s.com/datapitch/apply>. The application process was exclusively online. Submission consisted of a short proposal (around 5 pages), supporting documents, and a form with basic information about the company. The applicants were to be single companies (no consortia) and registered with the European Commission as an SME at the time of submission.

Before the call could be launched, significant work was done in preparing the data challenges. This involved targeting and inviting strategic data owners who had relevant needs that could best be served by bringing in strategic partners to develop solutions. Although one of the challenges was named Open Innovation, the vision behind Data Pitch is that all of the challenges would take the form of open innovation with all partners working together to achieve a mutually beneficial solution that a) could not have been achieved without the collaboration, and b) would not have occurred without Data Pitch's role as a broker.

The first call received 142 applications. Of these, 30 failed the eligibility test in not conforming to the clearly stated thresholds in the call document. The remaining 112 proposals were reviewed by a team of 9 reviewers drawn from across the consortium and representing a range of skill-sets. Numerical scores were used to filter down the evaluated applications, and eventually 57 SMEs were invited to interview in London.

The interviews with the SMEs took place between the 30th October and the 2nd November 2017 in London. The Data Providers were also present where relevant. Each interview lasted 45 minutes and the SMEs were given a strictly enforced 5-minute slot to deliver a pre-submitted PowerPoint presentation to a panel of three. Notes were taken and the panel stuck strictly to a prepared list of questions.

The contractual negotiation phase lasted from the outcome of the interviews on the 2nd November, until the accelerator launch event on the 1st February 2018. The goal of the contractual negotiation phase was to take the 18 SMEs that had been selected during the interview phase and get them started on the accelerator. The challenge was to enable all of the various businesses to sign up to the contract and pass all of the required checks.

The launch event took place on the evening of the 1st of February. This enabled the successful SMEs to introduce themselves, and also provided a networking opportunity with the Data Pitch team together with press, and relevant individuals from within the London startup ecosystem etc. The first day of support activities for the start-ups took place during the day of the 2nd of February 2018.

Overall the process worked well and the tools that were put in place for the first round served their purpose and should equally well serve for the second round call. The key benefit of having all

actions clearly recorded in one place that is shared across the project team is as a confidence booster in that the overall status of this phase of the project can clearly be seen.

The negotiation phase covered a short but intense burst of synchronised activity over seven months of the project. This process will be repeated for a second call later on in the project. A key purpose of this document is to inform and support that second call.

2. Introduction

The overall goal of Data Pitch is to accelerate the European data ecosystem, creating and supporting new businesses by unlocking the commercial potential of high-value datasets in a transnational, cross-sectoral data innovation ecosystem. This document describes the call for the first round accelerator for Data Pitch which will be coordinated and led by WP4. We cover the activities starting with the publication of the call to the invitation of the successful SMEs to the accelerator launch event in London. There are two acceleration phases in Data Pitch. These are the main actions contained within the project. Other activities support the acceleration phases and build upon their impact.

Data Pitch will seek to create a Europe-wide data innovation ecosystem that will bring together data owners and Big Data technology providers, with startups and SMEs with fresh ideas for data-driven products and services.

Accelerators are designed to be a practical and dynamic mechanism to drive forward the progress of selected SMEs in ways that would take them much longer individually and without such support. Drawing on the experience from key players in the consortium, we will establish a support structure for data-centric startups, guided and promoted by an international network of organisations and individuals.

The design and execution of the call format is a key instrument in achieving this. All of the consortium members are involved in various ways, and in our collaboration with data providers, we will support this emerging community.

Other work packages were very much involved in the process. WP2 provided input relating to the use of the data and experimentation facilities, technical support for datathons, and training activities for prospective applicants. WP3 delivered input for the definition of the tracks of the call and evaluation criteria, including quantifiable KPIs defined in collaboration with industry and data owners. WP4 was also closely aligned with WP6, which runs the Data Pitch information campaign, including call ads in digital form, presentations at various events, flyers, newsletters, and so on.

The call process capitalised on the competitive call toolkit setup by the University of Southampton and the Open Data Incubator for Europe (ODINE), which can be accessed via opendataincubator.eu. Overall, activity covered the definition of the call, training and support for potential applicants, the submission platform, and the selection of high-impact startups and SMEs.

3. Competitive call

A call was put out for SMEs ready to exploit the potential of data not available in the public domain. We describe the motivation, aims and objectives. The call is an open innovation mechanism designed to be an instrument to support data-driven entrepreneurship in Europe. The aim is to unlock data innovation. In terms of the call, this involved defining the process, soliciting and then selecting ideas. In terms of the accelerator this will include mentoring and support with business development.

3.1. Submission platform

Applications were to be made via the F6S platform. This platform is designed to connect tech

founders from 800k startups and more than 10,000 startup programs globally¹. The platform offered the opportunity to advertise and promote the Data Pitch call within the startup community, specifically targeting relevant and eligible startups through their scouting features. Additionally, by using this platform, the partners were able to draw on the support provided by F6S, which involved stakeholder communication through bespoke promotion, and monthly newsletters to the wider startup community. The application process itself was exclusively online. Submission consisted of a short proposal (around 5 pages), supporting documents, and a form with basic information about the company. The applicants were to be single companies (no consortia) and registered with the European Commission as an SME at the time of submission.

The platform was able to aggregate and visualise the status of applications, for example; showing applications that had been opened, completed or submitted (Annex 1). By having this feature, we were able to record and notify the applicants of their current stage, and the individual results of the process. However, functional issues were also encountered with the platform. These issues surrounded the review and evaluation process. The scoring system applied to Data Pitch did not complement that of F6S, which resulted in a longer offline Evaluation and Scoring process (Call Calendar in Table 1 below), due to the administrative time needed to translate these scores back into the F6S platform.

In order to truly evaluate the success of using this platform, partners will convene a review taskforce to establish what we need from F6S (or other systems) to determine what platform will be best for the second call. Below provides a timeline overview of the first competitive call as outlined in the application process

Table 1. Competitive call calendar

Stage	Date	Description
Publication	1 July 2017 12:00 pm CEST	Call is published on Data Pitch website
Guide for applicants	1 July 2017 12:00 pm CEST	Full guideline details published on website: http://datapitch.eu/apply/
Deadline	1 October 2017 12:00 pm CEST	Strict deadline for applications
Evaluation & scoring	2 October 2017 11 October 2017	Reviewers allocated set of applications to review, review process follows strict methodology
Panel review	13 October 2017	Review panel meet to review those applications that have met the threshold
Invite SMEs to interview	16 October 2017	Successful startups invited to interview, via the F6S platform
Interviews	30 October 2017 - 3 November 2017	Face to face interviews, held at the Digital Catapult, London, UK
Confirmation	6 November 2017	Successful SMEs notified that they have entered the contract negotiation phase
Negotiation	4 November 2017 -	Negotiation phase during which contractual

¹ <https://www.f6s.com/f6s>

	31 January 2018	obligations are checked including the workplans, data agreements, SME status and bank details
Launch	1-2 February 2018	SMEs invited to Accelerator launch in London

3.2. Data providers and challenges

Before the call could be launched, significant work was done in preparing the data challenges. This involved targeting and inviting strategic data owners who had relevant needs that could best be served by bringing in strategic partners who had specific challenges. These challenges were presented as challenges on the basis that they would allow startups to innovate with their data. Although one of the challenges was called “Open Innovation”, the vision behind Data Pitch is that all of the challenges would take the form of open innovation with all partners working together to achieve a mutually beneficial solution that a) could not have been achieved without the collaboration, and b) would not have occurred without Data Pitch’s role as a broker.

A number of data providers were invited to participate in the project and offer their private data for use by SMEs who could demonstrate that their app or service could both enhance the value of the data from the provider’s perspective and also help the SME in some way. The data providers’ data packages were promoted on the call under a range of themed challenges designed to attract different SMEs working in these areas. It is worth noting also that a collection of support documents were created and made available to applicants via the F6S application form.

The following challenges (see Table 2) were set up for the first call in 2017-2018. (New challenges will be set up for the second call in 2018-2019)

Table 2. Call challenges

Challenge identifier	Sector	Challenge	Data provider
DPC1-2017	RETAIL	Future-proof retail supply chains	<i>Sonae Center Servicos II, S.A.</i>
DPC2-2017	SPORTS & RECREATION	How can we use data to improve visibility and access to physical activities?	<i>imin Limited</i>
DPC3-2017	DATA ANALYTICS	Empowering sales and marketing decisions through company knowledge graphs	<i>SpazioDati</i>
DPC4-2017	TRANSPORT	Changing public transport for the better	<i>Deutsche Bahn AG</i>
DPC5-2017	DATA MANAGEMENT	The next generation of customer data management solutions	<i>UniServ GmbH</i>
SC1-2017	HEALTH & WELLNESS	How can we use data to help people improve their health and wellness and/or make health services more efficient and	<i>Please suggest your own data source</i>

		inclusive?	
SC2-2017	EMPOWERING USERS ONLINE	How can we use data to make the Web more trustworthy and improve personal safety and security online?	<i>Please suggest your own data source</i>
SC3-2017	LIFELONG LEARNING	How can we use data to ensure that we have and can further develop the skills we need in the future?	<i>Please suggest your own data source</i>
SC4-2017	LIVING	How can we use data to improve living standards and lifestyle, and create new accommodation options in Europe?	<i>Please suggest your own data source</i>
SC5-2017	SMART MANUFACTURING	How can we use data to make manufacturing, logistics and maintenance processes more efficient and able to support new models of use and repair?	<i>Please suggest your own data source</i>
SC6-2017	TOURISM	Transforming tourism: aggregated travel services and intelligent personal assistants	<i>Please suggest your own data source</i>
OIC1-2017	OPEN INNOVATION	Harnessing the full power of data-driven innovation	<i>Please suggest your own data source</i>

3.2. Relationship with applicants and datathons

During the first round of the call, prospective applicants were supported in a variety of ways. An email hotline (call@datapitch.eu) was set up and operated with a response time of 24 hours. In addition to this dedicated email hotline, potential applicants reached out to the Data Pitch team through the project's various outreach channels, such as the generic email info@datapitch.eu, the Data Pitch Facebook and Twitter pages, as well as the submission platform F6S.

Support was further provided to prospective applicants through an extensive number of Frequently Asked Questions on the Data Pitch website. These were updated to reflect answers provided through other channels to all the questions asked about Data Pitch, and thus ensure a fair and transparent competitive call. Training sessions in the form of webinars covered the overall objectives of the project, its methodology and specific guidance for the call, including timelines, application submission process, eligibility and funding criteria and evaluation procedures and deadlines. Two generic webinars were organised on 9 August and 12 September 2017, and one data provider specific webinar for SpazioDati took place on 18 September 2017 and had 232, 143 and 66 views on YouTube respectively (see the Data Pitch YouTube [channel](#) for more information).

The Data Pitch team did not organise any datathons for the first round of the competitive call. Indeed there was lukewarm reception from the data providers and concerns among the team that datathon as an instrument would not attract an audience relevant to the objectives of the project. Instead the Data Pitch team attended a datathon organised by one of the Data Providers, Deutsche Bahn Mindbox on 12-13 May 2017. Moreover, there will be a data exploration session

run with data providers, startups and SMEs at the Lisbon Investment Summit (LIS) on 6 and 7 June 2018.

Finally the Data Pitch team scouted potential applicants for the first call at a range of hackathons/datathons and events besides those mentioned above:

- Comtrade Digital Services 'Making smart mobility smarter' hackathon, Mentor and Jury Member - Berlin, June 2017
- Unbound July 2017
- PixelCamp - Lisbon, September 2017
- STHLMfest - Stockholm, September 2017
- Tech BBQ - Copenhagen, September 2017
- Pirate Summit - Cologne, September 2017
- Bitz & Pretzels - Munich, September 2017

3.3. Selection and review process for SMEs

The call received 142 applications from 23 countries within the H2020 network (see Figure 1 below). The full details of these are recorded in the project files.

Figure 1 Map of Data Pitch call - round 1 applicants

The map below shows the geographical spread of applicants. Data pitch received applications from 23 countries within the H2020 network.

Over 57% of applications were made to sectoral challenges, over 23% to data provider challenges

and 20% to open innovation ones. The five challenges that received the most applications were as follows:

1. Health & wellness (20.4%)
2. Open innovation (19.7%)
3. Smart manufacturing (11.3%)
4. Tourism (10.5%)
5. Empowering users online (9.9%)

More details are provided in Figures 2 and 3 below.

Figure 2 Number of applications per challenge

The chart below provides a more detailed breakdown of the number of applications per challenge, and those who made it through to the interview stage.

Figure 3 Number of applications interviewed per challenge

The chart below provides a more detailed breakdown of the number of applications per challenge, and those who made it through to the interview stage.

30 applicants failed the eligibility test in not conforming to the clearly stated thresholds in the call document. The remaining 112 proposals were reviewed by a team of 9 reviewers drawn from across the consortium and representing a range of skill-sets. The review process involved at least two reviews being conducted for each application and a range of technical and business perspectives applied across the board. A set of criteria guidelines was used for the evaluation process, and reviewers were required to provide a numerical score for key questions, as well as descriptive responses. The numerical scores (see blank version of the scoring spreadsheet [here](#)) were used to filter down the evaluated applications, and eventually 57 SMEs were invited to interview in London.

3.4. Interview process

The interviews with the SMEs took place between the 30th October and the 2nd November 2017 in London. The Data Providers were also present where relevant. Applicants were invited to attend using the letter format which can be found in Appendix 24: Data Pitch Interview.

Each interview lasted 45 minutes and the SMEs were given a strictly enforced 5-minute slot to deliver a pre-submitted PowerPoint presentation to a panel of three. Notes were taken and the panel stuck strictly to a prepared list of questions. For the three and a half days of interviews, two panels ran in parallel in adjacent rooms at the Digital Catapult in London.

Interviewees were advised that no direct feedback would be given to unsuccessful applicants, but that a blog post would be published that summarised (and anonymised) the common lessons learnt

and observations for general benefit.

The panel met at the end of the interview sequence and prioritised the candidates against the evaluated criteria and made a judgement on which SMEs should be invited to join the accelerator. There was no fixed threshold of numbers to pass, rather the threshold was based on quality, only those that passed the quality threshold, as well as the formal eligibility criteria, were invited to proceed.

The details of this process were tracked in the [spreadsheet](#). The key steps recorded in the spreadsheet were as follows:

- Total points
- Average Points
- Threshold of 60 Reached?
- Comments
- Date
- Time
- Invitation Sent in F6S
- Accepted
- Calendar Invitation Sent
- E-mail
- Country
- Information Pack
- E-mail with details
- Presentation
- Attendee (full list of team members attending)
- Panel
- Result
- Stage
- Confirmed
- Notes

Applications to all 12 challenges were interviewed in London, but only 8 were ultimately selected and represented in the Accelerator. Startups and SMEs from 9 countries within the H2020 network (see Figure 4) are currently represented in the first round of the Accelerator, working on the following challenges:

1. Health & wellness (4)
2. Smart Manufacturing (4)
3. Tourism (3)
4. Data management - Uniserv (2)
5. Data analytics - SpazioDati (2)
6. Transport - Deutsche Bahn (1)
7. Retail - Sonae (1)
8. Empowering users online (1)

Figure 4 Map of countries represented in the first round of the Accelerator

The map below shows the 9 countries that were represented by startups in Data Pitch. Hover over the country for the number of companies.

3.5. Contractual negotiation phase

The contractual negotiation phase lasted from the outcome of the interviews on the 2nd November, until the accelerator launch event on the 1st February 2018. The objective of the contractual negotiation phase was to undertake due diligence on the 18 SMEs that had been selected. The challenge was to enable all of the various businesses to sign the contract and pass all of the required checks. The aim was to avoid making any changes to the contract that has been agreed earlier in the project. This was challenging as all of the SMEs were at different maturity levels. Therefore, some had financial track records to draw upon, whereas others had to demonstrate their viability through their financial plans.

We also made use of the Commission's Participants Portal in order to check the SMEs status against their 9-digit Participant Identification Code (PIC) number. Companies need to register to obtain a PIC in order to join a consortium to apply for an EU call. As part of this relatively simple process, companies will be initially recorded as having a Declared status. Once they complete the application process the companies themselves will receive a response resulting from the self-assessment that they have been declared an SME. It was agreed that we would take such a form as evidence of their SME status and the other documents would not be needed. If any of the applicants have participated in an EU project in the past, then the Commission will have checked their status and, if appropriate, recorded them in the Portal as being Validated as an SME. Again, in this case, we would record the applicant as an SME and no other checks would be needed regarding their status.

Many members of the consortium were involved, either directly or indirectly, in the negotiation phase. In order to enable us to coordinate and drive this phase successfully we created a spreadsheet in the Project Google drive. This was called [Negotiation Tracker](#). This can be used as a template for the second acceleration phase. Initially, the spreadsheet contained a handful of columns named after the key steps in the negotiation document. SMEs are listed vertically on the left together with the legal name of the SME if different from the trading name, and the name of the main contact at the SME.

In addition to the main checks that were coordinated from Southampton, the ODI led the process of developing the workplans with the SMEs. SMEs were given a [template](#) to complete. Successful completion of the workplans was an obligatory component of the negotiation process. In turn, a sub-component of the workplan, was the generation of a viable financial budget plan. Breaking the task down into separate, sub-components enabled different members of the consortium to address budgets, workplans, SME status ([as defined by the EC](#)) and other elements such as data provision plans.

See Annex 7 for details of the required checks for SME status.

3.6. Accelerator launch

The launch event took place on the evening of the 1st of February. This enabled the successful SMEs to introduce themselves, and also provided a networking opportunity with the Data Pitch team together with press, relevant individuals from within the London startup ecosystem etc. The first day of support activities for the start-ups took place during the day of the 2nd of February 2018. The event was organised by the ODI and held at Runway East, Moorgate (Lower Ground, 10 Finsbury Square, London EC2A 1AF), a private office and co-working space environment for startups.

The Data Pitch project team met for a project meeting during the day of the 1st February to take advantage of being together in London and be briefed for the launch.

3.7. Call dashboard

A visual analysis of the first round of the call was produced (per T4.5) in the form of an infographic including a range of information on the applications received, interviews and funded.

It can be found on the data pitch website [here](#).

4. Lessons learned and next steps

In addition to the previous description of the process, we also added some reflections on the execution of the process that may be of help for the second round. Overall the process worked well and the tools that were put in place for the first round served their purpose and should equally well serve for the second round call. The key benefit of having all actions clearly recorded in one place that is shared across the project team is that it enables transparency and collaboration in that the overall status of this phase of the project can clearly be seen and next actions be clearly identified.

In terms of our relationship with applicants, the processes worked well. The data provider specific webinars proved highly useful and have been mandated for the second round of the call. Instead of organising datathons, which had proved only partially relevant and popular during the first call, a series of similar activities and workshops will be organised instead to address underserved geographical areas and small data providers.

The negotiation process also worked well, but the time frame is tight and challenging for all concerned. The expanded spreadsheet which now captures better the granularity of tasks will help next time. We also now have a better awareness of the inter-relationship and interdependencies between the parallel activities, and in particular how these are communicated to the SMEs. Specifically, the importance of the formal documentation to demonstrate SME status especially stamped bank documents, and the level of detail in the workplan budgets. Workplan budgets can be high-level in terms of activities and commitments but nevertheless should reflect a commitment to full engagement in the Data Pitch Accelerator Programme and adoption of the project's ethos in terms of costs and responsibilities.

5. Conclusion

The negotiation phase covered a short but intense burst of synchronised activity over 7 months of the project. This process will be repeated for a second call later on in the project. A key purpose of this document is to inform and support that second call. Overall the call was successful, 18 SMEs came on board out of a field of 142 applicants. Whilst tough for the field of competitors as a whole, this enabled Data Pitch to obtain a high quality selection ratio.

The process ran smoothly, albeit with hard work and diligence from the whole team, but the end result is a refined process which should greatly enhance the second call.

6. Annex 1: Data Pitch application status

Dashboard Apply Events Jobs Benefits Services Add your

Data Pitch Accelerator 17/18 x

Pipeline Pipeline Status Evaluation Funding Traction Markets Custom More

- In Progress
- Finalized
- Verified
- With Reviewer
- Data Provider
- Threshold Not Reached
- Threshold Reached
- Shortlisted for Interview
- Accepted
- Rejected
- Lead Not Contacted

Pipeline	Avg Score	Status	Markets	Location
Data Pitch ...rator 17/18	-	In Progress	-	-
Data Pitch ...rator 17/18	-	In Progress	-	-
Data Pitch ...rator 17/18	-	In Progress	-	-

Dashboard Apply Events Jobs Benefits Services Add your

Data Pitch Accelerator 17/18 x Finalized x Sort: Avg

Pipeline Pipeline Status Evaluation Funding Traction Markets Custom More

Pipeline	Avg Score	Status	Markets	Location
Data Pitch ...rator 17/18	-	Finalized	Health/Medical, Legal Services + 1	London, United Kingdom
#opendata #transparency #politics	-	Finalized	-	-
Data Pitch ...rator 17/18	-	Finalized	-	-
Data Pitch ...rator 17/18	-	Finalized	Consulting, Energy	Lille France

7. Annex 2: Guide for Applicants

The following information was provided for applicants:

Guide for applicants

(Data Pitch call 2017)

Call opens

1st of July 2017 at 12:00 noon CEST (Central European Summer Time)

Call closes

1st of October 2017 at 12:00 noon CEST (Central European Summer Time)

Note: Deadlines will be strictly adhered to. Any submissions past the deadline will not be considered.

Changelog

Version number	Date	Comment
1.0	30.06.2017	1 st version published online

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Introduction

This guide is designed to support applicants through the application process for the 1st Data Pitch call (2017). It is intended to be the main source of information for the Data Pitch call 2017. Therefore, in case of factual conflicts with other sources of information (such as the Data Pitch website), its contents should be deemed authoritative.

This guide should be consulted together the [Data Pitch 2017 challenges](#), which describe the topics funded by Data Pitch.

Should you have any outstanding queries regarding the application process following reading this document, please refer to the FAQ on our website or contact us at call@datapitch.eu.

What is Data Pitch

Data Pitch is a EU-funded **open innovation programme** bringing together corporate and public-sector organisations that have data with startups and SMEs that work with data.

It is centred around a **competition** with several tracks, which describe **challenges** set by the data-provisioning organisations, and an **accelerator programme** (6 months) to help startups and SMEs develop solutions to meet these challenges.

The startups and SMEs will put forward **proposals** for creating high impact, innovative products and services in response to the challenges defined by Data Pitch.

Successful applicants will receive an important financial and advisory boost to their idea, with support to develop a concept into a robust and sustainable data business.

Data Pitch is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, and is being delivered by the [University of Southampton](#), [Open Data Institute](#), [Beta-i](#) and [Dawex](#).

Competition

Two calls

The Data Pitch competition consists of **two calls**. The first call opens at 12 noon on the 1st July 2017 and closes at 12 noon on the 1st of October 2017. The second call is expected to open in summer 2018.

Three tracks

Each call consists of a series of **tracks** that refer to challenges which can be addressed by applicants:

- Track 1: Data provider challenges
- Track 2: Sector challenges
- Track 3: Open innovation challenge

Each challenge can be addressed via the use of one or more **datasets, open, shared or closed**. Each challenge is accompanied by examples of **expected outcomes** and **impacts**. Applications must target one challenge only, and explain how it will address it. For the 2017 Data Pitch call, startups and SMEs are allowed to submit multiple applications, but not for the same challenge.

In **track 1**, challenges are linked to **specific datasets**, which are provided by European businesses. The applicants must propose a solution that is relevant to the business problem and interests of the data provider. This solution must use the data mentioned in the challenge, possibly in combination with other datasets. Applicants must explain in their application how their idea is compliant with the data terms of use and, if applicable, relevant data protection regulations.²

In **track 2**, we grouped challenges from sectors that are very important for the EU economy. These challenges have been created via a **public consultation** and do not refer to any specific, closed datasets. In this case, the applicant is expected to identify the relevant datasets in their applications, and explain how their accessing at least one critical closed, third-party data resource makes their business idea possible. We would like to add that Data Pitch is an innovation programme exploring the potential of shared datasets for the EU data economy - applications using only open data or third-party data sourced by non-EU data providers will not be considered. Just like in the previous case, applicants will be asked to explain how their idea is compliant with the data terms of use and, if applicable, data protection regulations.

In **track 3**, we offer a platform for groundbreaking ideas that do not fit in the other tracks of the 2017 call. **This is not a track for incremental ideas**. Instead, it provides an opportunity for startups and SMEs that are working on something truly transformative; that can be applied over a wide range of industries; and has the potential to totally reinvent a process or find a solution for a previously unsolvable problem. This means that in track 3 we will consider only those applications that are real game changers, with high impact, that clearly unlock unrealised value in data and can articulate that value in a meaningful way.

We anticipate that most of the funding will be spent on applications submitted into track 1 and 2.

Challenges

The challenges covered by the 2017 call of Data Pitch can be found [here](#). Please read this document carefully to identify the challenge most relevant to you. Note the relevant datasets, as well as expected outcomes and impacts to guide you when you put together your application. If you have questions about a challenge or dataset please contact us at call@datapitch.eu. Do not contact the data providers about the Data Pitch challenges as they will not engage with applicants prior to the evaluation in any way.

² To note, the track 1 data provider challenges may be subject to revision in the event of changes in circumstances outside of the control of the Data Pitch consortium.

Online submission

Applications will be submitted online, using the [platform provided by Data Pitch](#). Applicants responding to a challenge in tracks 2 and 3 will be asked to prove they already have access to the closed datasets that enable their solution.

Evaluation and access to funding

Applications will be reviewed in **two steps**:

1. a **review**, based on predefined criteria (see also Annex 6). The result of the review will be a list of companies to be invited to a face-to-face interview in London early November.
2. an **interview** (approx. 45 minutes) with an expert panel.

Successful applicants at the interview stage will be invited to **negotiations**. During negotiations, you will discuss with Data Pitch the deliverables and milestones of your six-month accelerator project. During the accelerator, you will work together with mentors and advisors to help you grow your idea into a sustainable business.

Companies will not be required to relocate during accelerator, though they will be required to attend internal reviews and other Data Pitch relevant events. Companies responding to a data-provider challenge will be expected to engage with the data provider to gather feedback about the added value of their solution for the business problem described in the challenge. These conditions will be discussed in more detail during the negotiation phase (see also [How we select companies?](#) below).

Why join Data Pitch?

Startups and SMEs will receive funding and support for their data-centric business idea, including:

- Investment up to €100,000, equity free;
- Introduction to investors;
- Six-month business accelerator with the help of the [Open Data Institute \(ODI\)](#) and [Beta-i](#);
- Introduction to business partners sharing data via Data Pitch;
- Peer-networking and support via meetups in major European cities;
- Access to technology and datasets, as well as training and advice by Data Pitch experts.

Data Pitch builds on a series of similar publicly funded innovation instruments, including [ODINE](#) and the [ODI startup programme](#). You can learn more about our success stories [here](#).

Who is the funding for?

In order to apply for the call, **startups and Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)** must adhere to the definition as defined by the European Commission [here](#) and the [SME user guide](#). The funding is intended for **single entities**, rather than consortia of multiple entities. SMEs **legally registered in any of the EU member states or the associated countries** are eligible to apply for funding from Data Pitch; the list of relevant countries is provided in Annex 1 of this document.

Applicants must [register as an SME](#) with the European Commission prior to applying or the application will be automatically rejected. Please complete this registration prior to submitting your Data Pitch application - in the application you will be asked for a “PIC”, this is an identifier you will be allocated by the European Commission when you register with them. The registration process should be straightforward; however, please understand that your registering with the European Commission is not under the control of Data Pitch and we cannot help with any queries you might have about the process.

Data Pitch targets startups and SMEs who aim to build a business using data and data value chains.³ As noted in Section [Competition](#), applicants must target and apply for one particular track and challenge.

In summary, for applications to be considered for evaluation in the Data Pitch call, they must comply with the eligibility criteria as follows:

- The applicant must be an SME.
- The applicant must be legally established and working in the EU-28 countries or in the Horizon 2020 associated countries.
- The applicant must be registered with the European Commission as an SME at the time of submission.
- The applicant must be working as an individual company - no consortia will be permitted.
- The applicant must target one track and challenge, and propose a solution to that challenge, following the instructions laid out in the challenge text.
- The application must be complete and fulfill all criteria explained in Section [How to apply](#).

What is the funding for?

Successful applicants can use the Data Pitch funding in accordance with the Data Pitch contract between University of Southampton, as coordinator of Data Pitch and the SME (see Annex 7 of this document). The funding can be spent on salaries, equipment, consumables, travels, subcontracting to other parties (e.g., for marketing, training or legal support), and indirect expenditure (office space, office infrastructure etc. calculated as 25% of the total direct costs). In short, a Horizon 2020 budget distinguishes between four types of costs:

- Staff directly associated with the project.
- Other direct costs such as equipment, consumables, travels etc., which are relevant for the execution of the project.
- Subcontracting (e.g., for marketing, training or legal support).
- Indirect costs (also known as overhead) for items such as rent, admin staff, printing and photocopying, heating, electricity etc., calculated as a flat rate of 25% of the total direct costs.

As a participant in the Data Pitch programme, you may budget costs in all categories as long as they are eligible (see Annex 2 of this document for more explanations). All eligible costs will be fully reimbursed.

³ Data value chains describe the series of activities needed to generate value and useful insights from data.

The work you plan to carry out as part of Data Pitch cannot receive double funding. Synergies with other sources of funding, including other Horizon 2020 projects, are encouraged as long as the grants are used for complementary, not overlapping purposes.

Who keeps the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)?

You will be the sole owner of the results and outcomes of your project, and all associated IP. However, in track , data providers will be licensed the right to use (internally) any IPR you produce as part of the project, for one year after the project finishes. They may also impose additional licensing-related terms that will have to be honoured by winning applicants. Data Pitch itself will not retain an equity stake in your company, nor will it retain any IPR.

Additionally, Data Pitch or the European Commission may ask you to present your work as part of our public relations and networking events, in order to showcase the benefits of the innovation programme.

How to apply?

To apply for the Data Pitch call you are required to follow the process outlined below:

Step 1: Identify challenge

Go to datapitch.eu/apply/ and follow the instructions there. Consult the challenges and identify the one(s) relevant to you. As noted earlier, each SME will be allowed one application per challenge. An SME may submit multiple applications per call, but they must address different challenges.

Should your application be rejected in the 2017, a submission of the same proposal to the second call (in 2018) will be allowed. This does not provide you with any additional privileges over other second call applicants. Note that a resubmission is only possible if the 2018 call will maintain the relevant challenge from 2017 - Data Pitch cannot guarantee that this will happen, as the 2018 call will be based on a new consultation cycle which may result in a complete new set of challenges.

Step 2: Complete and submit application

Register on the [submission platform](#) and start preparing your application. You will be asked to

- provide some **basic information** about yourself and your company;
- complete all fields in the short proposal (Annex 3);
- agree to the terms in the **declaration of honour** and the **ethics statement** (refer to Annex 4 and 5 for templates of these documents); and
- upload all other documents required, as explained below.

In particular, for applicants addressing a sector challenge (track 2), you will be asked to provide **proof that you already have access to the data that your idea is built on**. The reason we are asking for this is because negotiating data access can be a tedious, lengthy process; In case your

application is successful, we will need you to have access to the data from the first day of your project.⁴

We will also ask everyone for

- a **pitch deck** (maximum 12 slides), viewed if you reach the interview stage; and
- a **short video** (1 minute), which explains why we should fund your team.

You may save your application and update it later or work offline and upload the information closer to the submission. We have prepared [a Google document with the short proposal template](#) (Annex 3), which you may want to use to prepare your application offline. This document also includes instructions about how to answer each question. We hope you will find it useful.

Fill out the all information required and upload all attachments. Only in this case your application will be considered for review. All information must be in English.

Once you press the submit button, **you will not be able to revise your application.**

Finally, please note that we cannot accept applications using other channels and cannot help retrieve or reopen any application once submitted.

How do we select companies?

Step 1 - Eligibility checks

Data Pitch checks if eligibility criteria are met. Proposals considered not eligible will not proceed to Step 2 of the evaluation process. The criteria are listed in [Who is the funding for?](#)

Step 2 - Review

Eligible proposals will be evaluated by at least **two reviewers** against the criteria listed in Annex 6 of this document.

The whole proposal adds up to 100 points, where the idea and impact account for a maximum of 30 points each and the team and budget are worth a maximum of 40 points. For each of the three areas, you will need to reach a **threshold**. These are:

- **15 points for idea and impact (each)**, and
- **20 points for team and budget.**

However, to be considered for an interview, you would need to reach a **minimum total of 60 points.**

The overall score will provide an internal **ranking** of applicants that will guide the decision of who is proceeding to Step 3.

⁴ Please understand that Data Pitch cannot support you in securing access to data, beyond the datasets described in the data provider challenges (track 1).

We will review applications on a first in, first served basis and we aim to inform successful shortlisted companies earlier so that they can have more time to book their travel and prepare. If you submit your application by September 1st, 12 pm CEST (firm deadline), we will inform you about the outcome of your application before the end of the call on October 1st.

Step 3 - In-person interview

Shortlisted companies will be invited to attend a **45-minute interview** in person, in London, UK with a panel. During the course of the interview, the applicant will present their proposal in a **short presentation (up to 5 minutes)**. The rest of the time will be used for **questions**. Interviewers may ask for documents or clarifications to be provided before the interview. We will also consider the pitch deck submitted with your application.

Interviews will be held in the **week starting from October 30th, 2017**. Please understand that we operate on a very tight schedule in order to grant challenge winners access to funding and support as quickly as possible. While we will aim to send out invitations to interviews by 16th October, we will not be able to change the week of the interviews or the slot allocated to you. Applications submitted before September 1st, 12 pm CEST will be notified earlier, as explain in the previous section.

We will not be able to negotiate interview dates or any other conditions of the interviews with any applicant and may not reply to any queries on the subject. If a company is not able to attend the interview in person, we will have to reject that application.

Travel expenses are not covered by Data Pitch.

After the interview, the panel will decide whether to accept the applicant into the Data Pitch programme. Notifications of acceptance or rejection will be sent out shortly following the interview process completion. Unfortunately, due to the high number of applications anticipated, we will not be able to provide feedback to applicants that have not passed Step 2. Decisions will be final and cannot be contested. We plan to inform applicants about the outcome by mid November.

Step 4 – Negotiation

If your application was successful, you will be invited to enter negotiations with Data Pitch. This is a busy four month period, which will hopefully end with a signed contract between you and Data Pitch. For this to happen, we will have to complete the following steps:

- **Due diligence checks:** Due diligence is performed on the status of the company. This will be in the form of checking the SME status of the company, validating company information, checking financial information, and performing other checks as required by the European Commission before entering onto the programme. Should a company fail the due diligence checks, Data Pitch reserves the right to reject the company's application.
- **Work plan agreement:** Before starting the accelerator, the applicant and Data Pitch agree on milestones and success criteria, as well as on the review and dissemination plan. For data-provider challenges, this stage might also involve discussions with representatives of the data provider. The applicant must provide the documentation required to finalise its acceptance into the programme as listed in Annex 7.

Negotiations will start mid November. They must finish (with a signed contract, see Annex 7) by the end of January, 2018. A detailed schedule will be sent out in due time.

Step 5 - Accelerator

Applicants who reach this stage of the process are formally accepted into the 6-month accelerator programme between February 2018 and July 2018.

Any funds will be transferred in stages as the agreed milestones are met. SMEs will be mentored by Data Pitch partners and external advisers. During the six months, the applicant will be asked to provide regular updates on their progress. In particular, they will be invited to attend a kick-off meeting of the cohort, as well as one or two review meetings (in-person) at key milestones in their project. Each SME will also be asked to support Data Pitch in increasing the public awareness of the project through attending conferences and networking events, both during the project and after graduation. In parallel, SMEs receiving the funding will receive promotion from our internal communications team - [Thwaites Communications](#).

Step 6 - Graduation

Successful SMEs from Step 5 will graduate from the accelerator programme. They cannot apply for the second call.

Annexes

Annex 1: Eligible countries

Only companies legally registered and operating in an EU member state or associated country are eligible to apply for funding from Data Pitch. Guidance on the associated countries can be found [here](#).

Annex 2: Eligible costs

Eligible means that the costs must be:

- incurred by your company in connection with your project;
- incurred by your company during the project;
- identifiable and verifiable in your accounts;
- compliant with national law;
- reasonable, justified, in accordance with sound financial management (economy & efficiency);
- indicated in the budget you submit in the short proposal.

Cost categories and reimbursement guidelines

The budget mentioned in the contract the SME signs with Data Pitch (see also Annex 7) includes different cost categories, which are explained below. There is a general distinction between direct costs, subcontracting, and indirect costs (also known as overheads). Indirect costs are calculated as 25% of the direct costs; no indirect costs can be charged on subcontracting.

All costs, except for purchased equipment (see below), will be reimbursed to 100%, including the indirect costs charged on top of the total direct costs. All costs should be stated inclusive of any irrecoverable VAT. Research grants are outside the scope of VAT and all input VAT on expenses directly related to the project will therefore be irrecoverable.

Direct costs: Personnel (100% reimbursed + indirect costs)

SMEs can spend Data Pitch funds on staff who are directly involved in the execution of the project.

Direct costs: Equipment (15% reimbursed + indirect costs)

Equipment with a useful life in excess of the project duration can only be reimbursed to the extent the asset would be depreciated for the six month project period. Therefore the standard rate allowed under the contracted project will be 15% of the total cost of the asset for a six month period. Indirect costs may be applied to the 15% of costs charged to the project.

The costs of equipment rental for the project period may be charged at full cost, as long as the rental costs is not greater than the depreciation cost had the equipment been purchased.

Direct costs: Consumables, other goods and services (100% reimbursed + indirect costs)

SMEs can spend in consumables and other goods and services (including travel) , if they are directly relevant for the achievement of the project.

Subcontracting (100% reimbursed, no indirect costs)

SMEs may subcontract some of their activities to other parties. No indirect costs (overhead) can be charged on subcontracting costs. Note that we expect the applicant to carry out most of the tasks of the project – subcontracting cannot be used to carry out key tasks in the project.

Indirect costs

Indirect costs are within the €100,000 limit and cover items such as rent, admin, printing, photocopying, amenities etc.. These costs are eligible if they are declared on the basis of the flat-rate of 25% of the eligible direct costs, from which are excluded:

- Costs of subcontracting and
- Costs of in-kind contributions provided by third parties which are not used on the SME's premises.

Annex 3: Short proposal

Idea (5000 characters)

Strength and novelty of the idea

<p><i>How do you propose to address the data challenge? What is your proposed solution?</i></p>	<p>1000 characters</p> <p>Clearly articulate your business proposal and its relevance to the challenge you are targeting.</p>
<p><i>How are you better than other solutions in this space? What makes your approach unique?</i></p>	<p>1000 characters</p> <p>Show us you know your business and are up to date about the most recent advances in the field. Be very specific about who your competitors are and how you compare against them. What is innovative in your proposal that will make you able to win a share of the market?</p>

Data value chain

<p><i>What does the data value chain of your solution look like? Which datasets will you use? How are they licensed? Explain how each dataset is relevant to your solution.</i></p>	<p>1000 characters</p> <p>List here the datasets that enable your idea. We need details about these datasets (domain, scope, main attributes, access, license) and how each of them help you build the solution from 1.1. You can also provide links to dataset descriptions, if available. Note that the reviewers will most likely not have the capacity to read extensive external documentation about these datasets. What they need is enough information to be able to assess that the dataset is relevant and valuable for your proposal.</p> <p>If you apply to a data-provider challenge, tell us about datasets that you plan to use in addition to the ones listed in the challenge (if any).</p> <p>If you apply to all other challenges, note that for your application to be considered, you need to propose an idea that is relevant to the scope of Data Pitch. Data Pitch is an innovation programme exploring the potential of shared datasets for the EU data economy -</p>
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	<p>applications using only open data or third party data sourced by non-EU data providers will not be considered.</p>
<p><i>What are the ethical and legal implications of the data value chain? If applicable, how will you deal with personal information?</i></p>	<p>500 characters</p> <p>Show us you have thought about these issues and you have a plan to master them.</p>

Outputs

<p><i>What will the tangible output(s) of your project be?</i></p>	<p>500 characters</p> <p>List here the specific outputs of the six months project. Consult the expected outcomes of the challenge you are addressing, they give you an idea about possible outputs reviewers would expect to see mentioned here.</p> <p>This section is about the product or service you will develop and the outputs should be related to that.</p> <p>Example: an Android app, with the following functionality....</p>
<p><i>How will you measure the quality of your outputs? Give examples of relevant KPIs.</i></p>	<p>1000 characters</p> <p>For each output, tell us how you will assess its quality. Mention the methods you will use, and relevant KPIs.</p> <p>If the challenge mentions any relevant KPIs, we would expect you to refer to them explicitly here.</p> <p>You do not have to limit yourself to the KPIs mentioned in the challenge. Every idea is different. Add those KPIs that will truly show the value of what you're proposing to do.</p> <p>Example: for our fictive Android app, you could consider a user study, focus groups etc. with a minimum number of users, number of downloads etc.</p> <p>As noted in the previous question, this part is about your product or service. Do not list any business KPIs here, focus only on product KPIs.</p>

Impact

Value proposition and potential scale

<p><i>What is your value proposition? Who are your customers?</i></p>	<p>1000 characters</p> <p>In the previous section, you told us why data is central to your proposal, here we we want to know about the business side of your idea. We expect a crisp value proposition and user stories, and details on how you fit in.</p>
<p><i>How will you make money? What is your revenue model and monetisation strategy?</i></p>	<p>500 characters</p> <p>Here you have a nice reference explaining the difference between revenue model and monetisation.</p> <p>https://www.quora.com/What-is-the-difference-between-a-revenue-model-and-a-monetization-model</p>
<p><i>What is the market segment and size you are addressing? Are you operating in a national or pan-European market?</i></p>	<p>500 characters</p> <p>Show us that you know your market, and that the share you are aiming at is large enough for you to be sustainable. Remember, the EU does not want a share of your company, it wants you to grow so you can contribute to economic growth and create employment.</p>

Market opportunity and timing

<p><i>Why is now a good time for your idea? Give an example.</i></p>	<p>500 characters</p> <p>For already established markets, convince us that it is not saturated and you can make a difference.</p> <p>For new markets, convince us that is it not too early for adoption and that you will have enough customers.</p>
<p><i>How many users and/or customers do you already have?</i></p>	<p>500 characters</p> <p>This value can be zero. We are happy to consider ventures at early stages, we asses the state of the market and the novelty of the idea to evaluate if we can fund you.</p>

What impact will your solution have

<p><i>What impact will your solution have? At the end of the Data Pitch programme, short term and long term. Be specific and quantify your impact.</i></p>	<p>1000 characters</p> <p>You previously explained to us how shared data is critical for your business idea and how a client would benefit from your solution. Here we want to know about the general impact: how much money does your product or service save your customer, your sector and maybe society as a whole? Does it help save costs, take better decisions, solve unsolved problems? Are there environmental or social benefits?</p> <p>Note that the challenges mention some areas of impact. We would expect you to refer to those relevant to you here.</p>
<p><i>Give a concrete example of the economic, societal or environmental impact your solution will have.</i></p>	<p>1000 characters</p> <p>Give us an example: whose lives are you going to change for the better and how? We do not expect 100% accuracy, but enough detail to understand the potential of what you're proposing.</p>

Team and budget (4000 characters + 1 minute video)

Knowledge and skills of the team

<p><i>List the core members of your team and their skills and experience. How many of them will be working full/part-time on the project?</i></p>	<p>1000 characters</p> <p>We refer here to the team that will work in the project. Remember we look for complementary skills in the core team. Please do not add any links to personal Websites, LinkedIn profiles etc. We will not have the bandwidth to check them. Use bullet points with name, role and relevant experience. Tell us if the team member is planned to work full time, part time or on a freelance basis on the project.</p> <p>Example: Mary, CTO, 10 yrs experience in backend dev, Ruby, Python, co-founded 1 startup and led a team of 5 developers, full time.</p>
<p><i>What skills/employees are still needed in your team to successfully execute the solution.</i></p>	<p>500 characters</p>

	<p>When critical skills are missing, we need to see that you are aware of the skills needed. You could use the Data Pitch funding to expand your team in those directions.</p>
<p><i>Why do you think that your team deserves to be in the programme?</i></p>	<p>Most startups and SMEs fail because they don't have the right team in place. What makes your team outstanding and the best mix of people to develop your idea and have a successful business?</p> <p>Tell us in a short video. We are not expecting professional content, we just want to get a sense of the core team and the main reasons we should fund you from the hundreds of other applications we receive.</p> <p>URL to 1 minute video (YouTube or Vimeo).</p>

Capacity to realise the idea

<p><i>What do think are the key elements necessary to execute your solution, what are you still missing and how do you expect to achieve them (i.e. funding, network, technology, etc.)?</i></p>	<p>500 characters</p> <p>We want to see you have thought things through and are planning ahead. Data Pitch can perhaps help you secure access to those missing pieces or give you mentoring and advice to succeed, in addition to the funding.</p> <p>Add other sources of funding needed, if any. Think one-year ahead.</p> <p>Not every idea, no matter how valuable, is suitable for a programme like Data Pitch. Some will require substantial amounts of investment beyond the 100k we can offer, major changes in the market or in regulations etc. We want to make sure Data Pitch can make a difference by selecting those idea which can truly benefit from its support and funding.</p>
<p><i>How can we help to bridge these needs?</i></p>	<p>500 characters</p> <p>You are in the driving seat, but we can help. Tell us how you could envision Data Pitch to support you realise your potential beyond the funding offered.</p> <p>Note, however, that we cannot help securing access to the datasets you listed in Section 1. Having access to that data from Day 1 of your</p>

	project is critical to the success of your application.
<i>What is your current monthly revenue (if applicable), burn rate and runway?</i>	250 characters Please indicate your burn rate, monthly revenue (if relevant) and runway.. If you are submitting a proposal for a side project and not your core business, please indicate the burn-rate for the project (or estimates, if you haven't started working on it yet), together with the company's burn-rate.
<i>What is your go to market strategy and timeframe?</i>	500 characters There is not one correct answer here. Show us you have thought about it and have a sensible plan.
<i>Indicate other sources of funding and how likely you are to secure them.</i>	250 characters What other investments (grants, debt, equity) are you currently seeking? This helps us assess your financial viability at the end of the accelerator.

Revenue forecasts

Revenue forecasts	2017	2018	2019
Revenues (€)			
Headcount (#)			

500 characters

Please provide a brief justification for your revenue forecast (e.g. customers, pricing, and market size) to show it is well founded.

Budget for the acceleration period (6 months)

1000 characters

Give a breakdown of how you will use the funding for personnel, subcontracting, travel, equipment, and other goods and services. Respect the following rules. Your application might be declared non-eligible if you fail to do so:

1. Describe costs only for the six months accelerator: 6 months and for a maximum of €100 000.

2. Remember that a flat overhead rate of 25% is applied to costs (except subcontracting).
3. Remember that due to European regulation, only 15% of purchased equipment can be reimbursed. Consult the guide for applicants for more details on eligible and reimbursed costs.

Annex 4: Declaration of honour

Declaration of honour on exclusion criteria and absence of conflict of interest

1. As legal representative of [insert legal entity name], I declare that the entity is not:
 - a) bankrupt or being wound up, is having its affairs administered by the courts, has entered into an arrangement with creditors, has suspended business activities, is the subject of proceedings concerning those matters, or is in any analogous situation arising from a similar procedure provided for in national legislation or regulations;
 - b) having powers of representation, decision making or controlling personnel being convicted of, or having been convicted of an offence concerning their professional conduct by a judgment which has the force of res judicata;
 - c) having been guilty of grave professional misconduct proven by any means which the contracting authority can justify including by decisions of the European Investment Bank and international organisations
 - d) failing to be compliant with obligations relating to the payment of social security contributions or the payment of taxes in accordance with the legal provisions of the country in which it is established or with those of the country of the contracting authority or those of the country where the contract is to be performed;
 - e) having powers of representation, decision making or controlling personnel having been the subject of a judgment which has the force of res judicata for fraud, corruption, involvement in a criminal organisation or any other illegal activity, where such illegal activity is detrimental to the Union's financial interests;
 - f) subject to an administrative penalty for being guilty of misrepresenting the information required by the contracting authority as a condition of participation in a grant award procedure or another procurement procedure or failing to supply this information, or having been declared to be in serious breach of its obligations under contracts or grants covered by the Union's budget.
2. I declare that the natural persons with power of representation, decision-making or control over the aforementioned legal entity are not in the situations referred to in b) and e) above.
3. I declare that I
 - a) am not subject to a conflict of interest and will take all reasonable measures to prevent any situation where the objectives of the Data Pitch project might be compromised due to undeclared shared interests;
 - b) have not made false declarations in supplying the required information to the project formally detailed as Data Pitch, and have not failed to supply the required information;
 - c) am not in one of the situations of exclusion, referred to in the abovementioned points a) to

f).

4. I certify that I:

- a) am committed to participate in the aforementioned project as part of the legal entity detailed above;
- b) have stable and sufficient sources of funding to maintain its activity throughout its participation in the aforementioned project, and will provide any counterpart funding necessary;
- c) have or will have the necessary resources as and when needed to carry out its involvement in the above mentioned project.
- d) will comply with my responsibilities and obligations under the Data Pitch project, including those set out in the Data Sharing Agreement.
- e) will respect any third party rights in relation to data provided for processing under the Data Pitch project.
- f) will abide by international, EU and national laws and regulations that might apply to the substance, or outcome, of data sharing arrangements as relevant to activities that I/my entity will be involved in under the Data Pitch project.
- g) will not share or disseminate data received through the Data Pitch project without the explicit prior consent of the data provider and any others with proprietary rights in relation to that data.
- h) will take all reasonable measures to safeguard data provided to me/my entity for use in the Data Pitch project against possible misuse and unauthorised access.
- i) will abide by international, EU and national laws imposing privacy and data protection requirements (including, in anticipation for its coming into effect, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (Regulation (EU) 2016/679)) as relevant. In particular, personal data shared under the Data Pitch project will not be re-used for purposes outside the project without the explicit prior consent of the data controller.
- j) will act in good faith as far as reasonably possible under the Project and fully apply the principles of the Ethics Statement.

5. I declare that, to the best of my knowledge, I am eligible to apply for the Data Pitch call and all the information I have provided is true.

Annex 5: Ethics statement

This Ethics Statement underpins the Data Pitch project in setting out specific rules and standards of conduct expected from recipients of Data Pitch funding. Ethical conduct means acting consistently in a way that is ethical and fair and encouraging others to do likewise.

The standard of behaviour expected is additional to compliance with relevant legal rights and obligations arising automatically by virtue of law applying to each participant. It is also not intended to exclude or replace responsibilities agreed under contract with the Data Pitch consortium (in case

your application is successful), as well as the certifications/declarations set out in the Declaration of Honour.

As legal representative of [insert legal entity name], I certify that [insert legal entity name] will adhere to the following principles as far as reasonably possible under the Data Pitch project:

1. act in good faith;
2. respect human rights;
3. ensure research quality and integrity;
4. be able to show that our findings are independent and non-discriminatory to any groups of individuals;
5. not misrepresent credentials;
6. demonstrate authenticity and validity of authorship;
7. respect confidential information;
8. secure any confidential information provided to prevent its misuse or unauthorised access;
9. only share confidential information where necessary and only where the prior informed consent of anyone potentially affected by the disclosure of such information has been received;
10. respect the privacy of any people identified from the findings of the Data Pitch project as far as possible;
11. avoid any conduct that may cause anyone harm, and seek relevant individuals' informed consent for any activities that might affect them directly;
12. determine the applicable laws that may apply to our activities under the Data Pitch project and plan our activities in accordance with such laws as early as possible;
13. not collect or otherwise process any personal or sensitive data not essential for our Data Pitch activities;
14. be fully transparent to the Data Pitch consortium about the purpose, methods and intended possible uses of our Data Pitch activities, and what risks, if any, are involved.
15. seek advice promptly from the Data Pitch consortium where we believe ethical and/or legal risks may be raised by our activities.

Annex 6: Review criteria

These are the review criteria which will be used in the selection of companies applying to Data Pitch. An application must receive at least 60 points to be considered for interviews. Thresholds for each section are provided in brackets.

Idea (0 to 30, minimum: 15)

Strength and novelty of the idea

- Is this novel in any way?
- Is it different from existing solutions?
- It is clearly described?
- Does it solve the challenge?
- Is it realistic in the time and budget?

Quality of the data value chain

- Do they have all relevant data?
- Are their datasets relevant to the challenge?
- Do they have any shared or closed data?
- Is it sufficiently European?
- Do they understand the ethical and legal issues?
- Do they have access to the data?

Outputs

- Are they clearly defined?
- Have they supplied relevant KPIs and baselines?

Impact (0 to 30, minimum: 15)

Value proposition and potential scale

- Is there a clear VP?
- Can they define their target customers?
- How clear is the revenue model and monetisation strategy?
- How clear is the market segment?
- How big is the market?
- How well does the business transfer to other EU markets?

Market opportunity and timing

- Is this a timely proposal?
- Does the solution have a customer base?

Expected impacts

- Are impacts clearly described?
- Are the impacts impressive?
- Are impacts linked to KPIs?

Team and budget (0 to 40, minimum: 20)

- Does the team have the skills to run the project?
- Does the team have the capacity to run the project?
- Does the team have a realistic understanding of their finances?
- Is the team committed to the project and their business?
- Is the revenue forecast realistic?
- Does the revenue forecast deliver convincing growth?
- Is the budget clearly described?
- Is the budget appropriate to realise the solution?

Annex 7: Negotiation documents

If you have passed the interview stage, you will be asked to submit a series of documents, as explained in this section.

Confirmation of SME status

Data Pitch must confirm your SME status as only SMEs can be recipients of its funding. In order for us to do so, you need to send us the following documents:

- Completed Legal Entity Identification form. The form can be found [here](#).
- SMEs self-check document and associated PIC (Participation Identification Code) number produced by EU Participant Portal. You have already produced these for the application.
- Company registration number & registration documents.
- Signed (and if applicable, stamped) copy of your company director's passport.
- Official VAT (or equivalent) document or – if you are not registered for VAT – proof of VAT exemption not older than 6 months.
- Balance sheet.
- Profit and loss accounts.
- Staff headcount expressed as full-time equivalents.

For **newly established enterprises** that have not yet closed accounts, we will require a self-declaration, including a bona fide estimate (in the form of a business plan) for the ongoing financial year.

For **enterprises without turnover**, whose activity implies a long time to market, we will require a declaration of the investment made and the expected return (to demonstrate that, despite the lack of turnover, the SME is engaged in an economic activity).

If the applicant has previously been validated by the European Commission as an SME (e.g., as past or current recipient of European funding), they should get in touch with us at negotiations@dataptich.eu. This might speed up negotiations significantly.

All documents must be in **English**. Data Pitch will not be able to accept documents in other languages. If the originals are not available in English, the SME will need to use a translation service and send us an **official translation**. Costs of translation are not covered by Data Pitch. Translation costs are not eligible for the funding received by the SMEs.

The SME status will be confirmed only if all documents listed so far will be submitted to Data Pitch in the form specified by given deadlines. Sworn or solemn statements before a judicial or administrative authority, notary, or public officer are **not acceptable proof** of SME status.

Bank account information

If negotiations are successful, Data Pitch will require bank account information of where to transfer the funding. SMEs will be asked to fill out this [bank information template](#).

The bank information document will have to be signed (and, if applicable, stamped) by the legal representative of your company. Use CAPITAL LETTERS and LATIN CHARACTERS when completing the form.

Project plan

During negotiations, the Data Pitch team will work with the SME to finalise a project plan for the six months accelerator programme. Receiving any amount of funding from Data Pitch requires the SME to **set and achieve** a set of milestones and/or KPIs. All milestones are signed off as completed by Data Pitch and potentially other mentors or advisors. When the applicant responds to a challenge set by a data provider, Data Pitch might define additional KPIs relevant to the data provider's economic activity.

The project plan will also include a revised budget. Data Pitch reserves the right to adjust the budget outlined by the SME in the original submission based on feedback received during the evaluation.

A preliminary template for the project plan can be found [here](#).

Contract

Once the applicant is validated as an SME and has negotiated the project plan with Data Pitch, they will be asked to sign a contract to formally join the Data Pitch accelerator. A preliminary template of the contract is available [here](#).

The terms of the contract are the same for every company accepted into the accelerator and cannot be negotiated.

Other documents

Data Pitch reserves the right to solicit any other document that allows Data Pitch to assess the financial health of the SME and its sustainability during and after the accelerator period.

Annex 8: General guidelines

The following general guidelines were provided to applicants.

General guidelines

This is a copy of the general guidelines for short proposals from the guide for applicants.

Applications in Data Pitch are submitted online. To be considered for review, applications must be complete (see also guide for applicants).

A core part of an application is the **short proposal**. Short proposals will be submitted via the online form made available via the F6S platform. **All questions must be answered according to the instructions provided by Data Pitch.** The questions help us assess your idea better; they make sure that you, the applicant is aware of the types of information we are looking for when judging whether your application deserves to be funded. The evaluation criteria we will follow

match these questions; more information about the evaluation is available in the guide for applicants.

When completing the form, please note these rules:

1. Answer each question. If you think a question does not apply to your case, explain briefly why.
2. Be **clear and concise** and respect the instructions about the length of each answer. The clarity of your writing will be a critical factor in convincing the reviewers that your company deserves to be shortlisted for a face-to-face interview. Feel free to use bullet points instead of full sentences or descriptive paragraphs when relevant.
3. Write for an informed audience that is familiar with the general context of the data challenge you respond to, but not with the particulars of your business, data value chain, or market.
4. The online form does not support any visual elements, for example figures or tables. You will be allowed to use those if you are shortlisted for an interview.
5. Do not include any links to external documents to answer a question. Your proposal must be **self-contained** and describe everything you want Data Pitch to know about your idea. The only exception allowed is the link to the video from Section 3.1 (see next).
6. One of the questions in Section 3 asks you to submit a **1 minute video** with the answer. This helps us get to know your team better.
7. The budget must be for the **6-months acceleration** period and for an amount **<= €100.000**.

Proposals that do not respect one or more of the above rules will be declared **non-eligible** and **discarded without a review**.

Instructions for completing Section 3

In **Section 3.1** you will be asked to tell us **why we should fund your team**. The answer to this question must be provided via a **short video** (1 minute long). The video should be uploaded to **Youtube as unlisted or Vimeo as private with the URL added into the application**. The quality of the video will not be judged and we do not expect any edits or effects. Please include key team members who will be involved in building your solution in the video. Videos will not be watched for longer than 1 minute.

In **Section 3.3**, please complete the **revenue forecast question** and add a brief **justification** (one paragraph) for your forecast (e.g., customers, pricing, and market size) in the relevant field.

In **Section 3.4**, please provide a **breakdown** of how you will use the funding for personnel, subcontracting, travel, equipment, and other goods and services. Then, provide a short explanation of what you are going to spend the funds on (e.g., CEO salary, subcontract legal advice, travel to a customer meeting etc.). When completing Section 3.4, please respect the following rules;

your application might be rejected if you fail to do so:

1. Describe **only costs that are covered by Data Pitch**.
2. Remember that a flat overhead rate of 25% is applied to costs (except subcontracting).
3. Remember that due to Horizon 2020 regulations, only 15% of purchased equipment can be reimbursed. Consult the guide for applicants for more details on eligible and reimbursed costs.

Further information

- The reference document containing all the relevant information about the Data Pitch

competition is the guide for applicants. You will find a copy of this document in the guide.

- Consult our FAQ for specific questions.
- A guide for better writing: [The Day You Became A Better Writer](#)

Data Pitch Interview

The following letter was sent to those SMEs selected for interview:

Dear startup,

We hope you are doing well and you are ready for the Data Pitch interview.

We want to let you know that we are very excited to meet you all in London next week!

Here are a few things you need to know:

Your interview will be 45 minutes;

You will have max 5 minutes to present;

You are welcome to use a deck for your presentation. The format should be pdf or keynote;

The location will be Digital Catapult Centre, 101 Euston Rd, Kings Cross, London NW1 2RA.

If you are intending to present with slides please send them to us by the 27th of October at 12pm midday UTC (UK time)

Your panel will consist of 3 members of the Data Pitch consortium and a possible observes. Please see the panel for your presentation below:

Elena Simperl - The University of Southampton

Heidi Lindvall - The Open Data Institute

Bashara Hinnawi - Beta-i

Ryan Goodman - The Open Data Institute - Observer

Please remember to arrive at least 10 minute before your allocated interview slot.

We are looking forward to meeting you in London!

Best Regards,

DataPitch Team